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CEF 444: AI & ML**

HYPER PARAMETERS TUNING AND MODEL SELECTION

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I. INTRODUCTION

Every single machine learning model selection is a major exercise and it is purely dependent on selecting the equivalent set of hyper parameters.

Choosing the right model is very technical and is affected by some factors such as: nature of the data, hyper parameters, nature of the problem, model performance requirements, scalability and much more. The aim of this document is to explain how hyper parameters affect the choice of a ML model by tuning the hyper parameters of three different models and evaluating their accuracy.

II. DEFINITION OF KEY TERMS

1. Model:

A model in machine learning is a mathematical representation of a real-world process. It is trained on historical data to recognize patterns and make predictions or decisions based on new data. Examples include Logistic Regression, Decision Trees, and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN).

2. Parameters:

Parameters are the learned internal coefficients and weights of a machine learning model that are adjusted during training to fit the model to the data. *For example*, in a linear regression model, the slope and intercept of the line are parameters.

3. Hyper parameters:

Hyper parameters are configuration settings used to control the learning process and the structure of the machine learning model itself. Unlike model parameters, hyper parameters are set before the training process begins and are not learned from the data. Examples include the learning rate in gradient descent, the depth of a decision tree, and the number of neighbors in KNN.

4. Hyper parameter space:

The hyper parameter space is the range of values that hyper parameters can take. It represents all possible combinations of hyper parameters that a model can use. For instance, if tuning a decision tree, the hyper parameter space might include different values for *max_depth*, *min_samples_split*, and *criterion*.

5. Hyper parameter tuning:

Hyper parameter tuning is the process of finding the optimal combination of hyper parameters for a machine learning model. This process aims to maximize the model's performance by systematically searching through the hyper parameter space and evaluating the performance of different hyper parameter combinations. Effective hyper parameter tuning can significantly improve model accuracy and generalization to new data.

6. Grid Search:

Grid Search is a hyper parameter tuning method that exhaustively searches through a manually specified subset of the hyper parameter space. It evaluates all possible combinations of hyper parameters specified in a grid format. Although comprehensive, it can be computationally expensive, especially with large hyper parameter spaces.

7. Random Search:

Random Search is a hyperparameter tuning method that randomly samples the hyperparameter space and evaluates a fixed number of hyperparameter combinations. This approach is often more efficient than Grid Search, particularly when dealing with a large hyperparameter space, as it can potentially find good hyperparameters with fewer evaluations.

III. MACHINE LEARNING LIFE CYCLE: HYPERPARAMETER TUNING AND ITS TECHNIQUES

The ML life cycle involves several stages, including data collection, preprocessing, model training, evaluation, and deployment. Among these stages, hyperparameter tuning is a critical step that significantly impacts model performance. This section elaborates on the process and results of hyperparameter tuning using Grid Search and Random Search for three different models: Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN).

1. Problem Definition

The first step in the ML life cycle is identifying the problem to be solved and defining the objectives. For this project, the problem is to predict diabetes based on various health-related features. The objective is to build a predictive model that can accurately classify individuals as diabetic or non-diabetic based on the provided features.

2. Data Collection

Data collection involves gathering relevant data from various sources that can be used to train and evaluate the model. For this project, the diabetes dataset was selected. This dataset contains medical diagnostic measurements for a number of patients and includes features such as Pregnancies, Glucose, BloodPressure, SkinThickness, Insulin, BMI, DiabetesPedigreeFunction, and Age. It also contains a label column which are the outcomes of each record in the dataset.

```
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score
✓ 0.0s

# Load dataset into a pandas dataframe
data = pd.read_csv("diabetes.csv")
data.head()
```

	Pregnancies	Glucose	BloodPressure	SkinThickness	Insulin	BMI	DiabetesPedigreeFunction	Age	Outcome
0	6	148	72	35	0	33.6	0.627	50	1
1	1	85	66	29	0	26.6	0.351	31	0
2	8	183	64	0	0	23.3	0.672	32	1
3	1	89	66	23	94	28.1	0.167	21	0
4	0	137	40	35	168	43.1	2.288	33	1

3. Data Preprocessing

Data preprocessing involves cleaning and transforming the dataset to make it suitable for modeling. In this project, the following preprocessing steps were undertaken:

- **Handling Missing Values:** Missing values in the dataset were converted to NumPy NaNs, and each NaN field was populated with the mean of the elements in its column.
- **Feature and Target Division:** The dataset was split into input features (X) and the target variable (y).
- **Data Splitting:** Subsequently, the data was divided into training and testing sets to ensure that the models could be trained and evaluated on separate data.

```
# Mark zero values as missing or NaN
data[['Glucose', 'BloodPressure',
      'SkinThickness', 'Insulin', 'BMI']] = data[['Glucose', 'BloodPressure',
      'SkinThickness', 'Insulin', 'BMI']].replace(0, np.NaN)
```

✓ 0.0s

```
# Fill missing values with mean column values
data.fillna(data.mean(), inplace=True)
```

✓ 0.0s

```
# Split dataset into inputs (X) and outputs (y)
X = data.iloc[:, 0:8].values
y = data.iloc[:, 8].values
```

✓ 0.0s

```
# Split the data into training and testing sets
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)
```

4. Model Selection and hyper parameter calculation

Model selection involves choosing the appropriate machine learning algorithms based on the problem and the characteristics of the data. For this project, three models were selected to determine which one would yield the best results for the diabetes prediction task. Also, both Grid Search and Random Search techniques were used to tune the hyperparameters for each algorithm.

```
# Now lets use Grid search to tune the hyperparameters
from sklearn.model_selection import GridSearchCV
from sklearn.model_selection import RandomizedSearchCV
```

These models and their hyperparameters are:

- **Logistic Regression:** A linear model used for binary classification problems.

Hyperparameters:

- 'C': Inverse of regularization strength. Smaller values specify stronger regularization.
- 'max_iter': specifies the maximum number of iterations that the solver can use to converge to a solution.
- 'dual' Boolean parameter that determines whether to solve the dual or primal optimization problem.

```
# Create the logistic regression model
from sklearn.linear_model import LogisticRegression
lr = LogisticRegression(solver='liblinear')
```

✓ 0.0s

```
# Lets define a grid of hyperparameters for lr.
param_grid = {
    'dual': [True, False],
    'max_iter': [100, 110, 120, 130, 140],
    'C': [1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5],
}
```

✓ 0.0s

```

# Let's run the grid search and see the results with execution time.
import time

grid = GridSearchCV(estimator=lr, param_grid=param_grid, cv = 3, n_jobs=-1)

start_time = time.time()
grid_result = grid.fit(X, y)
# Summarize results
print("Best: %f using %s" % (grid_result.best_score_, grid_result.best_params_))
print("Execution time: " + str((time.time() - start_time)) + ' ms')

```

✓ 0.2s

Best: 0.764323 using {'C': 2.0, 'dual': False, 'max_iter': 100}
 Execution time: 0.17810845375061035 ms

```

# Let's run the random search over them and see the results with execution time.
random = RandomizedSearchCV(estimator=lr, param_distributions=param_grid, cv = 3, n_jobs=-1)

start_time = time.time()
random_result = random.fit(X, y)
# Summarize results
print("Best: %f using %s" % (random_result.best_score_, random_result.best_params_))
print("Execution time: " + str((time.time() - start_time)) + ' ms')

```

✓ 0.1s

Best: 0.764323 using {'max_iter': 130, 'dual': False, 'C': 2.0}
 Execution time: 0.08038997650146484 ms

- **Decision Tree:** A non-linear model that splits the data into subsets based on feature values.

Hyperparameters:

- *'max_depth'*: The maximum depth of the tree. Controls the complexity of the model and helps to prevent overfitting.
- *'min_samples_split'*: The minimum number of samples required to split an internal node
- *'min_samples_leaf'*: The minimum number of samples required to be at a leaf node.

```
from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeClassifier
dt = DecisionTreeClassifier(random_state=42)
```

✓ 0.0s

```
# Lets define a grid of hyperparameter and apply grid search.
param_grid = {
    'max_depth': [None, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50],
    'min_samples_split': [2, 5, 10],
    'min_samples_leaf': [1, 2, 4]
}
```

✓ 0.0s

```
# Let's run the grid search over them and see the results with execution time.
import time
```

```
grid = GridSearchCV(estimator=dt, param_grid=param_grid, cv = 3, n_jobs=-1)
```

```
start_time = time.time()
```

```
grid_result = grid.fit(X, y)
```

```
# Summarize results
```

```
print("Best: %f using %s" % (grid_result.best_score_, grid_result.best_params_))
```

```
print("Execution time: " + str((time.time() - start_time)) + ' ms')
```

✓ 0.2s

Best: 0.713542 using {'max_depth': 10, 'min_samples_leaf': 2, 'min_samples_split': 2}
Execution time: 0.2350008487701416 ms

```
# Let's run the random search over them and see the results with execution time.
```

```
random = RandomizedSearchCV(estimator=dt, param_distributions=param_grid, cv = 3, n_jobs=-1)
```

```
start_time = time.time()
```

```
random_result = random.fit(X, y)
```

```
# Summarize results
```

```
print("Best: %f using %s" % (random_result.best_score_, random_result.best_params_))
```

```
print("Execution time: " + str((time.time() - start_time)) + ' ms')
```

✓ 0.1s

Best: 0.701823 using {'min_samples_split': 10, 'min_samples_leaf': 1, 'max_depth': 20}
Execution time: 0.0722966194152832 ms

- **K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN):** A non-parametric model that classifies instances based on the majority class among the k-nearest neighbors.
 - *'n_neighbors'*: Number of neighbors to use.
 - *'weights'*: Weight function used in prediction.
 - *'metric'*: Algorithm used to compute the nearest neighbors.

```
from sklearn.neighbors import KNeighborsClassifier
knn = KNeighborsClassifier()

✓ 0.1s

param_grid = {
    'n_neighbors': [3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 14],
    'weights': ['uniform', 'distance'],
    'metric': ['euclidean', 'manhattan', 'minkowski']
}

✓ 0.0s
```

```
# Let's run the grid search over them and see the results with execution time.
import time

grid = GridSearchCV(estimator=knn, param_grid=param_grid, cv = 3, n_jobs=-1)

start_time = time.time()
grid_result = grid.fit(X, y)
# Summarize results
print("Best: %f using %s" % (grid_result.best_score_, grid_result.best_params_))
print("Execution time: " + str((time.time() - start_time)) + ' ms')

✓ 0.3s

Best: 0.740885 using {'metric': 'manhattan', 'n_neighbors': 14, 'weights': 'distance'}
Execution time: 0.265674352645874 ms
```

```
# Let's run the random search over them and see the results with execution time.
random = RandomizedSearchCV(estimator=knn, param_distributions=param_grid, cv = 3, n_jobs=-1)

start_time = time.time()
random_result = random.fit(X, y)
# Summarize results
print("Best: %f using %s" % (random_result.best_score_, random_result.best_params_))
print("Execution time: " + str((time.time() - start_time)) + ' ms')
✓ 0.1s

Best: 0.736979 using {'weights': 'distance', 'n_neighbors': 13, 'metric': 'manhattan'}
Execution time: 0.056018829345703125 ms
```

5. Model Training and Evaluation

Model training involves fitting the selected model(s) to the training data. This process adjusts the model's parameters to minimize the error on the training data. At this stage, two models of each ML algorithm were trained with hyperparameters obtained from both grid and random search. The models were evaluated to assess the performance using evaluation metrics, primarily the accuracy, which measures the proportion of correctly predicted instances out of the total instances.

- **Logistic Regression models:**
 - *With grid search Hyper parameters:*

```
# Create the logistic regression model with grid hpp
lr2 = LogisticRegression(solver='liblinear', C=2.0, dual=False, max_iter=100)

# Fit the model on the training data
lr2.fit(X_train, y_train)

# Make predictions on the test data
y_pred = lr2.predict(X_test)

accuracy = accuracy_score(y_test, y_pred)
print(f"Accuracy: {accuracy * 100:.2f}%")
✓ 0.0s

Accuracy: 76.62%
```

- *With random search Hyper parameters:*

```
# Create the logistic regression model with random hpp
lr3 = LogisticRegression(solver='liblinear', C=2.0, dual=False, max_iter=110)

# Fit the model on the training data
lr3.fit(X_train, y_train)

# Make predictions on the test data
y_pred = lr3.predict(X_test)

accuracy = accuracy_score(y_test, y_pred)
print(f"Accuracy: {accuracy * 100:.2f}%")
```

✓ 0.0s

Accuracy: 76.62%

- **Decision Tree models:**

- *With grid search Hyper parameters:*

```
# Decision Tree with grid hpp
dt1 = DecisionTreeClassifier(random_state=42, max_depth=10, min_samples_leaf=2, min_samples_split=2)
dt1.fit(X_train, y_train)
y_pred_dt = dt1.predict(X_test)
print(f"Decision Tree Accuracy: {accuracy_score(y_test, y_pred_dt) * 100:.2f}%")
```

✓ 0.0s

Decision Tree Accuracy: 74.68%

- *With random search Hyper parameters:*

```
# Decision Tree with random hpp
dt2 = DecisionTreeClassifier(random_state=42, max_depth=20, min_samples_leaf=1, min_samples_split=10)
dt2.fit(X_train, y_train)
y_pred_dt = dt2.predict(X_test)
print(f"Decision Tree Accuracy: {accuracy_score(y_test, y_pred_dt) * 100:.2f}%")
```

✓ 0.2s

Decision Tree Accuracy: 72.73%

- **K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) models:**
 - *With grid search Hyper parameters:*

```
knn1 = KNeighborsClassifier(metric='manhattan', n_neighbors=14, weights='distance')
knn1.fit(X_train, y_train)
y_pred_dt = knn1.predict(X_test)
print(f"KNN Accuracy: {accuracy_score(y_test, y_pred_dt) * 100:.2f}%")
```

✓ 0.0s

KNN Accuracy: 73.38%

- *With random search Hyper parameters:*

```
knn2 = KNeighborsClassifier(metric='manhattan', n_neighbors=13, weights='distance')
knn2.fit(X_train, y_train)
y_pred_dt = knn2.predict(X_test)
print(f"KNN Accuracy: {accuracy_score(y_test, y_pred_dt) * 100:.2f}%")
```

✓ 0.0s

KNN Accuracy: 74.03%

6. Model selection:

After the hyper parameter tuning, it is necessary to conclude on which model will be selected as the best model to implement this scenario of diabetes prediction. For that, let us be based on the metric of accuracy of the different models with the different hyper parameters obtained from grid and random search.

Accuracy	Grid Search	Random Search
Logistic Regression	76.62%	76.62%
Decision Tree	74.68%	72.73%
KNN	73.38%	74.03%

From the accuracies above, the best model to predict diabetes with the chosen dataset is logistic regression model. This is because it produces a higher accuracy when tested over the test data.

IV. CONCLUSION

Through this project, we demonstrated how tuning can significantly impact model performance, ultimately leading to the selection of the most effective model for predicting diabetes. The insights gained from this process underscore the importance of hyperparameter optimization in building robust and accurate machine learning models.